

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus by imidazolium fluorochromate

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Abstract : Oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus by imidazolium fluorochromate (IFC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding oxyacids with phosphorus in a higher oxidation state. The reaction exhibits 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The reaction is first order with respect to IFC. A Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics was observed with respect to the reductants. The reaction does not induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Reactions are catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of deuteriated phosphinic and phenylphosphinic acids exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. The oxidation was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effects were analysed in terms of Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The effect of solvent indicates the solvent polarity plays a major role in the process. It has been shown that the pentacoordinated tautomer of the phosphorus oxyacid is the reactive reductant and it has been concluded that tricoordinated forms of phosphorus oxyacids does not participate in the oxidation process. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

Keywords : Halochromates, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, phosphorus acids.

Introduction

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. Imidazolium fluorochromate (IFC) is also one of such compounds used for the oxidation of benzylic alcohols⁶. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and several reports on halochromates have already reported from our laboratory⁷⁻¹⁰. Further the lower oxyacids are reported to exist in two tautomeric forms^{11,12}, and it is of interest to determine the nature of the oxyacid acid involved in the oxidation process. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of oxyacids of phosphorus by IFC. Therefore, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of phosphinic (PA), phenylphosphinic (PPA) and phosphorous (POA) acids by IFC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as a solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to IFC. The reactions exhibited the Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics with respect to the oxyacids (Table 1). A plot of $1/[\text{Oxyacid}]$ versus $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ is linear

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Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of oxyacids of phosphorus by IFC at 298 K

10^3 [IFC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Oxyacid] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)		
		PA	PPA	POA
1.00	0.10	2.03	7.54	0.70
1.00	0.20	3.23	10.9	1.08
1.00	0.40	4.51	14.1	1.48
1.00	0.60	5.20	15.6	1.69
1.00	0.80	5.62	16.4	1.81
1.00	1.50	6.36	17.9	2.03
1.00	3.00	6.87	18.8	2.17
2.00	0.40	4.95	14.4	1.51
4.00	0.40	4.14	13.5	1.35
6.00	0.40	4.80	14.0	1.44
8.00	0.40	4.22	15.3	1.53
1.00	0.20	3.51 ^a	11.7 ^a	1.10 ^a

^aContained 0.005 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

with an intercept at the rate-ordinate (Fig. 1). This indicates the following overall mechanism (eqs. (1) and (2))

and the rate law (3).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{IFC}] [\text{Oxyacid}] / (1 + K [\text{Oxyacid}]) \quad (3)$$

The dependence on reaction rate on reductant concentration was studied at four different temperatures and the value of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic and activation para-

Fig. 1. Oxidation of POA acid by IFC : A double reciprocal plot.

eters were also calculated from the values of K and k_2 , respectively, at different temperatures (Tables 3 and 4). Fig. 2 depicts a typical kinetic run.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile/test for free radicals : The oxidation of oxyacids, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile did not affect the rate. This indicates that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in the present reaction (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm^{-3} of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain importance of the cleavage of the P-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of deuteriated PA and POA was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 3).

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 2). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the

Table 2. Effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the oxidation of PPA by IFC

[IFC] = $0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; [PPA] = 1.0 mol dm^{-3} ; Temp. = 298 K						
[H ⁺]	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	8.55	9.72	12.6	15.3	18.9	21.6

Table 3. Rate of decomposition constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of phosphorus-oxyacids-IFC complexes

Acid	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				K	ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288	298	308	318				
PA	3.78	7.47	14.4	27.9		48.1 ± 0.5	125 ± 2	85.1 ± 0.4
PPA	11.7	19.8	32.4	55.8		36.9 ± 0.7	154 ± 2	82.7 ± 0.6
POA	1.26	2.34	4.50	8.28		45.4 ± 0.6	143 ± 2	88.0 ± 0.5
DPA	0.61	1.27	2.62	5.37		52.6 ± 0.6	124 ± 2	89.5 ± 0.5
DPOA	0.21	0.40	0.82	1.58		49.0 ± 0.9	146 ± 3	92.3 ± 0.7
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	6.12	5.88	5.50	5.19	(PA)			
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	6.00	5.85	5.48	5.24	(POA)			

Table 4. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of the oxidation of phosphorus-oxyacids-IFC complexes

Acid	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				K	$-\Delta H^*$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^*$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288	298	308	318				
PA	4.41	3.81	3.15	2.58		16.2 ± 0.6	35 ± 2	5.75 ± 0.5
PPA	6.84	6.15	5.40	4.70		12.0 ± 0.4	18 ± 1	6.96 ± 0.2
POA	4.95	4.31	3.60	2.97		15.5 ± 0.6	32 ± 2	6.06 ± 0.5
DPA	4.05	3.55	2.93	2.43		15.6 ± 0.7	34 ± 2	5.56 ± 0.5
DPOA	5.58	4.90	4.32	3.70		12.8 ± 0.4	22 ± 1	6.42 ± 0.3

Fig. 2. Oxidation of POA acidity by IFC : A typical kinetic run.

following form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and b , for PPA, are $6.84 \pm 0.21 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $14.7 \pm 0.35 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively at 298 K ($r^2 = 0.9977$).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of PPA was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of IFC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values formation constants K and decomposition constants k_2 at 298 K for the oxidation of PPA are recorded in Table 5. The formation constant of the intermediate complex, K , did not vary much with the solvent but the rate constant, k_2 , exhibited much variation in values with different solvents.

Reactivity oxidizing species : The observed hydrogen-oxidation dependence suggests that the reaction follows two

mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of IFC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (4).

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC⁷ and QFC⁸.

Solvent effect : The rate constants of the oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (LESR) of Kamlet and Taft¹³ (5).

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (5)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (6), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (6)–(9).

$$\log k_2 = -3.90 + 1.86 (\pm 0.25) \pi^* + 0.35 (\pm 0.21) \beta + 0.46 (\pm 0.19) \alpha \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8616; \text{sd} = 0.23; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.99 + 2.03 (\pm 0.27) \pi^* + 0.19 (\pm 0.22) \beta \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8057; \text{sd} = 0.26; n = 18; \psi = 0.47$$

Table 5. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of phenylphosphinic acid by IFC at 298 K

Solvents	K ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$10^4 k_2$ (s^{-1})	Solvents	K ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$10^4 k_2$ (s^{-1})
Chloroform	5.85	33.9	Toluene	4.52	12.0
1,2-Dichloroethane	4.59	51.3	Acetophenone	5.45	79.4
Dichloromethane	6.03	41.7	THF	5.49	24.5
DMSO	6.15	198	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	6.44	13.8
Acetone	5.83	47.9	1,4-Dioxane	5.39	20.9
DMF	5.76	95.5	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	5.04	11.0
Butanone	5.49	37.2	CS_2	4.47	5.25
Nitrobenzene	4.63	63.1	Acetic acid	5.18	2.82
Benzene	5.72	14.8	Ethyl acetate	5.88	17.0
Cyclohexane	4.15	0.85			

It is thus seen that $k_2 = k_a = k_b$, which means that the rate constant for the decomposition of the complex is not affected by the reactive form of the phosphorus oxyacid. However, $K = K_1 K_b$, so that $K_b = 10^{-12} K$ or K_b for PPA should have value of the order of 10^{12} . Generally chromium(VI) does not give rise to extensive and highly stable series of complexes¹⁷. Further, the reported values^{5,18,19} of the formation constant for the chromic acid-PPA complexes are 6.12 ± 0.3 , 11 ± 2 and $19 \pm 4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Similarly, the formation constant of complex²⁰ between triethylamine and Cr^{VI} diperoxide derivative is $0.0014 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Thus the very high value of formation constant of present oxidant-phosphorus oxyacid complex is improbable, and it is highly unlikely that the tricoordinated form is involved in the oxidation process.

Mechanism :

The absence of any effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate and the failure to induce polymerization

of acrylonitrile point against a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of a P-H bond in the rate-determining step. A preferential cleavage of a P-H bond, in the rate-determining step, is likely in view of the relatively high bond dissociation energy of the O-H bond. The mean value of the bond dissociation energy of an O-H bond²¹ is 460 kJ mol^{-1} , while that for a P-H bond²² is 321 kJ mol^{-1} . Therefore, a hydride ion mechanism may be proposed for the oxidation of these oxyacids.

The proposed mechanism involving the hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step is also supported by the observed major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

It has already been shown that both PCC^{23} and PFC^{24} act as electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility, ESR and IR studies.

Scheme 1

In the chromic acid oxidation of phosphinic acid Sengupta and Chakaldar¹⁹ postulated the participation of tricoordinated tautomer. However, no evidence has been presented and author did not take into consideration the small value of K_t . However, Sharma and Mehrotra¹⁸ reported that in the chromic acid oxidation it is not possible to pinpoint the reactive form of the compound. The formation of a phosphinium ion in the rate-determining step has been postulated by the earlier workers^{18,19}.

It is of interest to compare the mode of oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus by PFC²⁵, PCC²⁶ and IFC. The oxidation by FCC exhibited the second order kinetics, first with respect to each reactant. The oxidation by PFC and IFC presented similar kinetic picture i.e. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics. The rate-law, acid dependence, kinetic isotope effect are similar in both the cases. In all the three oxidations, excellent correlation were obtained in terms of Swain's equation with the cation solvating power of the solvents playing the major role.

The rate of oxidation follows the order : PPA > PA > POA. The faster rate of PPA could be explained on the basis of stabilisation of a positively polarized phosphorus, in the transition state, by the phenyl group through resonance. The slower rate of POA may well be due to the electron-withdrawing nature of hydroxyl group causing an electron-deficiency at the phosphorus atom. This makes the departure of an anion more difficult. A perusal of the activation parameters in Table 3 revealed that the reaction rates are controlled mainly by the entropy of activation.

Experimental

The phosphorus oxyacids were commercial products (Fluka) and were used as supplied. IFC was prepared by the reported method⁶ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method and melting point determination. Deuteriated phosphinic (DPA) and phosphorus acids (DPOA) were prepared by repeatedly dissolving the acid in deuterium oxide (BARC, 99.4%) and evaporating water and the excess of deuterium oxide *in vacuo*²⁷. The isotopic purity of the deuterated PA and POA, as determined from their NMR spectra, was $92 \pm 5\%$ and $94 \pm 5\%$ respectively. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in non-polar

solvents like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Other solvents were purified by their usual methods.

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus leads to the formation of corresponding oxyacids containing phosphorus in a higher oxidation state. Reaction mixtures were prepared containing a known excess of phosphinic or phosphorous acids. On completion of the reaction, the amount of phosphorous formed in the oxidation of phosphinic acid and the residual reductant in the oxidation of phosphorous acids were determined by reported method²⁸. To determine the stoichiometry of the oxidation of PPA, a known excess of IFC was treated with PPA and the residual IFC was determined spectrophotometrically at 352 nm after the completion of the reaction. The oxidation state of chromium in the completely reduced reaction mixture, determined by iodometric titration, was 3.96 ± 0.10 . The oxidation exhibited 1 : 1 stoichiometry and the overall reaction may therefore, be written as :

IFC undergoes two-electron change. This is in accordance with the earlier observations with other halochromates.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the [Oxyacid] over [IFC]. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed by monitoring the decrease in the [IFC] spectrophotometrically at 354 nm for up to 80% reaction. Pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from linear plots ($r > 0.9990$) of $\log [\text{IFC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rates were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants, k_2 , were determined from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Oxyacid}]$.

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